

University Career Administrators' Perception of Job Rotation and Its Influence on Productivity

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Abstract

The study investigated University career administrators' perception of the influence of job rotation on their productivity indices. The entire population of 624 career administrators was used. Two research questions were answered and two null hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance. The questionnaire on job rotation and productivity indices (QJRPS) used for data collection was structured and built on a 4-point rating scale. The data collected in the study were analysed, using the following statistical tools: weighted mean (\bar{x}) in conjunction with a measure of variability (SD), t -test analysis was employed in testing the null hypothesis 1 at the 0.05 level of significance, while ANOVA was used to answer null hypothesis 2. The study revealed among others, that career administrators in Nigerian Universities have positive attitude towards job rotation. Based on the findings, educational implications were highlighted while appropriate recommendations were also made among which is the use of productivity indices to study the views of university career administrators on productivity and job rotation irrespective of their ranks.

Introduction

The drastic changes in the movement of women into the labour force have made mothers at all level, especially those in tertiary institutions to face numerous challenges to which they must respond. Demands from work place such as taking of minutes of meetings, supervision of students' projects, marking of examination answer scripts, teaching of large classes in the mist of inadequate resources and facilities, coping with students' needs coping with administrative rules and so on are some of the tasks faced by working mothers in tertiary institutions. Working mothers are married women who are working in tertiary institutions. Ukavbe (2009), referring to these demands, opined that academic staff of universities are faced with numerous challenges and demands from students and administrative authority to the extent that they are over worked.

Apart from the numerous challenges working mothers face in their offices, they also have additional responsibilities which include child care, school run, preparation of food, management of household and their other duties as house wives. Sometimes, their office responsibilities

compete with home demands. For instance, a working mother whose baby becomes sick and she should attend to health need of the child promptly, at the same time, she may be called urgently to come to the office the same day, to prepare voucher for salary or any other emergencies. In attempt to meet with these multiple responsibilities, working mothers become exhausted, confused and stressed.

Stress is a disruption of emotional stability of an individual which induces a state of disorganization personality and behavior (Selye, 2000). Okolocha (2008) defined stress as any environmental situation which creates tension and imbalances within and outside an individual's level of productivity. To Wiley (2000), stress is a biological phenomenon that is experienced by all persons regardless of their socio-economic status, occupation or age.

Stress is also viewed as the way individuals respond to conditions that scare, threaten, anger bewilder or excite them. For the purpose of this study stress is imbalance or tension experience by individual in an attempt to cope with challenges of life. Stress is an unavoidable part of life. People experience it in varying forms and degrees every day. Stress sometimes is not bad especially when it is moderate, it can actually be beneficial. Stress helps to compel people to action, it can result in a new awareness and exerting new perspective. However, stress can affect individual's physical, mental and social functioning when it is too much. In this case it can be destructive.

Stress does not exist on its own - there must be demands that trigger the stress and these demands or causes are called stressor, Stressors are situations which can trigger stress such situations include marking of answer scripts after examinations, teaching of large classes, and supervision of projects, dispatching of mails, minuting on mails, meeting up with administrative rules and orders updating knowledge through research, lack of annual leave among-others. Domestic stressors include child care, school run, and preparation of food, caring for husband, daily hassles church meetings, community meetings and traffic delays.

Winfield (2000) indicated that there is prevalence of occupational stress among academic and general staff of universities, Olumuse (2006) also observed that there are stressors that adversely affect academic staff of universities. She enumerated such as supervising students project more than a staff can conveniently handle, inadequate facilities such as class rooms, offices, teaching aids, marking of examination answer scripts and refusal to, pay lecturers' salary due to late submission of students' results. Moreover, Fie and Alam (2009) identified stress inducing factors in academic staff to include work overload, home work interface, role ambiguity and performance pressure. In addition to this, Ahmandy, Changiz, Masiello and Brommels (2007) included workload, conflicts, demands from colleagues and supervisors, incompatible demands from different personal and organizational roles, inadequate resources for appropriate performance, incompetency in the demands of roles, inadequate autonomy to make decision on different tasks and feeling of under utilization as sources of stress among academic staff of universities. Ofoegbu and Nwadiani (2006) also revealed significant factors influencing stress among academic staff to include strike and school interruption, delay and irregular payment of salary, lack of instructional facilities, preparation of results, invigilation of examination, campus militancy, high cost of living, lack of offices and accommodation, lack of annual leave/holiday

and underfunding of education. Perhaps this is why Akubue (2002) stated that working in tertiary institution as an academic staff is a stressful occupation and the extent to which different staff of tertiary institutions cope with the stressors determine the attainment of the objective of the institutions.

Working mothers in tertiary institutions have numerous roles that make them candidates of stress. The home and the office are in a dynamic reciprocal relationship, sometimes stress from the home can be brought to the office. This is in accordance with the principle of transferable of stress. According to Pleck, (2000) stress among working mothers is associated with long working hours, traveling away from home and "spillover of fatigue, preoccupation and irritability from work to family and from family to work. Consequently, any minor irrational behaviour from the husband, children or dependants results in disproportionate hostility, On the other hand, stress generated in the home, say death of spouse, death of children, and behavior of children could also be transferred to work place. This creates or link between stress in the home and at the work place. Some working mothers have little babies in hand. This adds more stressors because work associated with new born baby is always tedious, On the other hand, some young mothers may be pregnant; pregnant women always suffer from pregnancy related illness and at the same time must do their work, both at home and in their offices. Findings by Hinshow (2006) pointed out that working mothers are more under stress than non-working mothers. He continued by saying that work sometimes puts women into unhappy situations thus making their level of stress to be higher.

Stress is unavoidable in life and the effects sometimes are dangerous. Making adjustment to stress therefore, becomes imperative in order to reduce its negative effects on the body. When working mothers in tertiary institutions are unable to cope with the stressors, their levels of stress will be high resulting to exhaustion and negative consequences like depression, low productivity, absenteeism among others. According to Obi and Obi (2001), negative effect of stress could be classified into; emotional, cognitive and physiological. Emotionally, most working mothers in tertiary institutions seem to manifest unpleasant feelings of anxiety depression and anger, cognitively, severe stress can disrupt their thinking, mental images, concentration and memory. Physiologically, working mothers under prolonged stress could show some symptoms like headache, tension and weakness, pains and heart diseases. Immune mechanism reduction digestive disorder and cancer among others. Working mothers might have these experiences depending on their level of stress. Therefore, it become obvious and necessary that there is need for identification of levels of stress of individuals especially working mothers who have multiple responsibilities to attend to.

Statement of Problem

Effects and consequences of stress are evident in the health of Nigeria, work force including working mothers in tertiary institutions in Anambra State. It has numerous effects, ranging from poor job performance, mental illness, anxiety, low self esteem, depression, high blood pressure, premature death and headache (Ngoka, 2000). Based on bad effects of stress on people, researchers have worked on stress, levels of stress among academic staff in tertiary institutions. Akubue (2000) stated that working in tertiary institution is a stressful occupation

Smith and Bourk (2000), UK Health and Safety Executive (2000), reported that two out of every five teachers, were highly stressed against one in every other occupations like nursing, management, road haulage and security.

Although these studies were focused on Lecturers in tertiary institutions, there was no evidence of studies on the levels of stress among working mothers who are over burdened with multiple responsibilities both at home and in their work places. The question that arise are therefore: what are the levels of stress among working mothers in tertiary institutions in Anambra State? The answers to these questions will form the body of this study.

Research Questions

What are the levels of stress experienced by working mothers in tertiary institutions in Anambra State?

Null hypotheses

There is no significant difference in the mean scores of teaching and non-teaching working mothers on the level of stress they experienced.

Methods

Research Design

The design adopted in this study was descriptive survey research design. According to Nwogu (2006) survey research design is one in which a group of people or items is studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few people considered to be representative of the entire group. This design was chosen for this study because the researcher chose few working mothers considered to be representative of the study group.

Scope of the Study

This study was limited to all the working mothers in the five Government tertiary Institutions in Anambra State, The population of working mothers in the five tertiary institutions is 2,911. These institutions include Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka, 1,269 working mothers Emeka Odimegwu Ojukwu university Uli (351) Federal Polytechnic Oko, (450) Federal College of Education Nsugbe 435 working mothers)

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample size for this study is comprised of 630 working mothers sampled from a population of 2,911 working mothers in the five tertiary institutions used for the study. The sample was gotten through proportionate stratified random sampling of the working mothers. The stratification was based on institutions. The details of the sample size are Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka 137 teaching working mothers and 138 non teaching working mothers, Emeka Odimegwu Ojukwu University Uli 38 teaching working mothers and 38 non teaching working mothers Federal Polytechnic Oko, 49 teaching working mothers and 48 non teaching working mothers. Federal College of Education (Technical) Umunze, 44 teaching working mothers and 44 non teaching working mothers, Nwafor Orizu College of Education Nsugbe, 47 teaching working mothers and 44 non working mothers, given a total of 630 working mothers.

Instrument for data Collection

The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire which was developed by the researcher and it was tagged "Levels of Stress Among working mothers in tertiary institutions in Anambra State. (LSAWMTIASQ) items in the questionnaire were derived from information obtained from literature reviewed. The questionnaire has two sections A and B section A deals with personal data of the respondents while section B covers the Psychological Emotional, Physiological and cognitive symptoms of stress. The instrument has a five point scale weighted as follows:

1. VH Very high 5 points
2. H High 4 points
3. M Moderate 3 points
4. L Low 2 points
5. VL Very Low 1 point

Validation of the instrument

Validation is concerned with the extent to which an instrument measures what it was designed to measure (Welsh & Williams Ihecoins, 2001) in order to achieve this, the instrument was given to four experts in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka for assessment. These experts following the detailed scrutiny affirmed that the instrument covered the intended content areas and was therefore valid for use.

Reliability of the Instrument

The researcher used split half method of reliability to determine the reliability of instrument. The odd numbered items and even numbered items were administered separately to a group of working mothers in Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba. The split half reliability coefficient was determined by correlating the scores on the odd numbered items against the scores of the even numbered items. This yielded 0.65. Co-efficient which was corrected to 0.79 by the application of the spearman - Brown prophecy formular (Akuezuilo & Agu 2007).

Method of Data Analysis

The researcher employed both range of scores to answer the research question and t test to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The options that represent the various stress levels were assigned as follows: very high (5 point), high (4 points), moderate (3 points), low (2 points) and very low (1 point). To ensure uniformity in rating scale, the instrument was rated as follows from

1-1.49 which is 40 - 59.60 very low

1.50 - 2.49 which is 60 - 99.60 low

2.50 - 3.49 which is 100 - 139.60 moderate

3.50 - 4.49 which is 140 - 179.60 high

4.50 - 5.00 which is 180 - 200.00 Very high

Presentation and Analysis of Data

Research Question

What are the levels of stress experienced by working mothers in tertiary institution in Anambra State.

Table 1: Range of scores of working mothers' experienced levels of stress.

Range of Scores	N	%	Remark
40.00-59.60	17	3	very low
60.00 - 99.60	174	28.06	low
100.00-139.60	273	44.03	moderate
140.00-179.60	144	23.22	high
180.00-200.00	12	.1.94	very high

Table 1 shows that 12 (1.94%) working mothers with the scores ranging from 180.00 to 200 experience very high level of stress. 144(23.22%) of the working mothers who scores between 140.00 to 179.60 experienced high level of stress. Also scored 100.00 and 139 (28.06%) of them with scores ranging from 60.00 to 99.60 experience low level of stress, while 17 (3%) of the working mothers who scored between 40.00 and 59.60 experience very low level of stress in their work place.

Testing the Hypothesis

Null hypothesis

There is no significant difference in the mean scores of teaching and non teaching working mothers on the level of stress they experience in tertiary institutions.

Table: t-test on the mean scores of teaching and non -teaching staff working mothers on their level of stress in tertiary institutions.

Source of variation	N	X	Sd	df	Cal.t	Crit.t	P>0.05	Remark
Non Teaching	312	122.36	31.53	618	3.80	1.96		S
Teaching	308	112.97	29.99					

S= significant.

Table 2, shows that at 0.05 level of significant and 618 df of the calculated t 3.80 is greater that the critical ti.96. Therefore, there is significant difference in the mean score of teaching and non teaching working mothers of teaching and non teaching working mothers on their levels of stress in tertiary institutions. Also the non teaching working mothers experience more stress with mean difference of 9.39.

Discussion of the Finding/ Result

According to the result as presented in table 1 out of 620 working mothers used in the study, 144 (23.22%) has high level of stress 12(29) working mothers experienced very high level of stress. This is in support of by Ofoegbu and Nwachiani (2006) who reported that lectures in Nigerian Universities were one of the occupational groups that function under the conditions of high stress. Also this study is in line with Okolocha (2008), Ukavbe, (2009), Egwunyenga and Egbule (20030 and Ebiai (2010). Who confirmed that University workers are prone to stress. Although all these studies were done in the universities but this present studies is on tertiary in situations which comprises of universities, college of educations and polytechnic. The high level of stress experienced by working mothers might be as result of so many responsibilities and commitments. Perhaps they might be ignorant of the dangers of high level of stress or that they are not exposed on how to curb their stress levels.

For those working mothers who are experiencing moderate level of stress, 273 (44.03%) have relatively normal stress, effort should be made for them to maintain such levels. Also some of the working mothers experience low and very low level of stress 174 (28.00%) and 17 (3%) respectively. The result of the low level of stress might of be that they are not bordered about what others are doing or that they are non challant about life. Some of them might be those who are not serious with their work both at home and in the work place. This means that they might be neglecting their duties. The result in table 2 shows that non teaching working mothers have more stress than teaching working mothers with mean score of 122.36 and 112.96 respectively. The difference in their mean is 9.39. This implies that non teaching working mothers are experiencing more stress than the teaching working mothers. This may be a result of their work schedule or time schedule.

Based on the presentation, it is obvious that working mothers in tertiary institutions are experiencing high level of stress. This situation can be attributed to lack of exposure or ignorance on the part of the working mothers in tertiary institutions towards the dangers of high level of stress. These problems calls for urgent solution on how to curb their stress level.

Recommendations

1. Management of tertiary institutions should create a compulsory leave or holiday for working mothers in tertiary institutions and also reviews the work load in tertiary institutions and makes some adjustment in order to reduce levels of stress of working mothers in tertiary institutions.
2. Management of tertiary institutions should endeavour to recruit more staff in order to reduce the work load on existing staff, also create job specifications.
3. The management of tertiary institutions should regularly organize in service education programme such as conferences, workshop and seminars to educate participants on stress adjustment patterns. This will give working mothers in tertiary institutions the full knowledge of stress, stress level and stress adjustment patters.
4. Guidance counsellors should plan for group guidance regularly to guide working mothers in tertiary. This will give working mothers in tertiary institutions on the right pattern in of stress adjustment to use and dangers of high level stress.

5. Government and management of tertiary institutions school provide recreational facilities in tertiary institutions for working mothers to relieve tensions.

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